

Fig. 1. Plots of induced shifts ($\Delta\delta$) vs metal concentrations, $\text{Eu}(\text{DPM})_3/\text{substrate}$.

The large paramagnetic shift of H-1 relating to H-10 indicates that the hydroxyl group to be *syn* to H-1 as in 1. The fact that the paramagnetic shift of H-2 occurring to a lesser extent than the H-1 also supports the above view.

Experimental

^1H Nmr spectra (60 MHz; CDCl_3) were recorded with TMS as an internal reference on a Varian A-60D spectrometer at 45° , and ir spectrum (nujol) on a Perkin-Elmer 720 spectrophotometer.

Preparation of oxime derivative of β -naphthol-maleic anhydride adduct: β -Naphthol-maleic anhydride adduct prepared⁹, was refluxed with equimolar amounts of hydroxylamine hydrochloride and pyridine in ethanol for 2 h. Crystallisation of solid mass obtained upon addition of water yielded 1, m.p. $170-71^\circ$ (Found: C, 63.03; H, 4.43. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4$ requires: C, 63.16; H, 4.51); ν_{max} 3 550, 3 200, 1 780, 1 720 and 1 600 cm^{-1} .

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Studies on Thiourea Derivatives. Part-III. Preparation and Antimicrobial Activity of *p,p'*-Bis(*N*-thioureidocarbonyl- methoxyphenyl)sulphones

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THIOUREA derivatives have been found to possess wide therapeutic activities¹. Some thioureas have been found to be useful as insecticides². Hence, we have undertaken the preparation of some substituted-phenylthioureas bearing *p,p'*-dihydroxydiphenylsulphone moiety.

p,p'-Dihydroxydiphenyl sulphone (1) was condensed with chloroacetic acid to get *p,p'*-bis(carboxymethoxy)diphenylsulphone (2). The acid was refluxed with thionyl chloride to get the acid chloride (3), which was then treated with different

phenylthioureas to get the derivatives of type 4. The structural assignments of the products were based on their elemental, ir and pmr spectral data. The products were screened for their antimicrobial activity.

Antimicrobial activity : The antimicrobial screening of thiourea derivatives was carried out using cup-plate method³ at a concentration of 50 µg ml⁻¹ using gram-positive bacteria *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Staphylococcus citreus*, gram-negative bacteria *Escherichia coli*, *Marcasane serratia* and fungi *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, *Aspergillus niger*. The results showed that most of the compounds are moderately active against different strains of bacteria and fungi (11–18 mm, zone of inhibition). However, comparatively maximum activity was observed in compounds having (alongwith zone of inhibition in mm) R=phenyl (16–18), 2-tolyl (16–18), 3-tolyl (15–18), 2-anisyl (16–22),

3-anisyl (18–18), 3-carboxyphenyl (16–18), 4-carboxyphenyl (15–19), 3-chlorophenyl (17–18), 2-nitrophenyl (16–18), 3-nitrophenyl (16–19), 4-nitrophenyl (18–18), 4-acetylphenyl (16–18) and 4-carbomethoxyphenyl (16–18).

Experimental

Melting points of the compounds were determined in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. Structures of the compounds were established on the basis of their elemental and spectral data. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Shimadzu DR-1, 435-IR spectrophotometer in the range 4000–400 cm⁻¹, and pmr spectra on a XL-100A, 100.1 MHz spectrometer using TMS as internal reference.

p,p'-Bis(carboxymethoxy)diphenylsulphone (2). To a mixture of *p,p'*-dihydroxydiphenylsulphone (12.5 g, 0.05 mol) and chloroacetic acid (9.45 g,

TABLE 1 – ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF *p,p'*-BIS (*N*-ARYLTHIOUREIDOCARBONYLMETHOXYPHENYL)SULPHONES

Sl. no.	R	M.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula	N% : Found/ (Calcd.)
1.	Phenyl	146	73	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₆ S ₂	8.84 (8.82)
2.	2-Tolyl	148	78	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₆ S ₂	8.42 (8.45)
3.	3-Tolyl	103	62	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₆ S ₂	8.35 (8.45)
4.	4-Tolyl	220	72	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₆ S ₂	8.46 (8.45)
5.	2-Anisyl	132	76	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₆ S ₂	8.08 (8.06)
6.	3-Anisyl	106	52	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₆ S ₂	8.01 (8.06)
7.	4-Anisyl	134	68	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₆ S ₂	8.07 (8.06)
8.	2-Carboxyphenyl	170	56	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₁₀ S ₂	7.81 (7.75)
9.	3-Carboxyphenyl	160	69	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₁₀ S ₂	7.74 (7.75)
10.	4-Carboxyphenyl	132	78	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₁₀ S ₂	7.69 (7.75)
11.	2-Chlorophenyl	187	78	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ Cl ₂ N ₄ O ₆ S ₂	7.71 (7.96)
12.	3-Chlorophenyl	142	66	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ Cl ₂ N ₄ O ₆ S ₂	7.89 (7.96)
13.	4-Chlorophenyl	158	72	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ Cl ₂ N ₄ O ₆ S ₂	7.92 (7.96)
14.	2-Nitrophenyl	155	76	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₁₀ S ₂	11.56 (11.59)
15.	3-Nitrophenyl	167	82	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₁₀ S ₂	11.58 (11.59)
16.	4-Nitrophenyl	101	79	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₁₀ S ₂	11.51 (11.59)
17.	Benzyl	116	56	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₆ S ₂	8.51 (8.45)
18.	4-Ethoxyphenyl	144	72	C ₂₂ H ₂₄ N ₄ O ₆ S ₂	7.72 (7.75)
19.	4-Acetylphenyl	209	64	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₆ S ₂	7.84 (7.79)
20.	4-Carbomethoxyphenyl	168	68	C ₂₃ H ₂₄ N ₄ O ₁₀ S ₂	7.16 (7.19)

0.1 mol), a solution of sodium hydroxide (8.96 g, 0.244 mo) was added slowly with stirring. The contents were heated until most of the liquid evaporated and the residue was treated with water (250 ml) and cooled. The clear solution was then acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid and the resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol-water (3:1) solvent, (13.91 g, 16%), m.p. 243° (Found: C, 52.49; H, 3.80; S, 8.69. $C_{16}H_{14}O_3S$ requires: C, 52.4; H, 3.85; S, 8.75%); ν_{max} (KBr) 920-880 br (OH, o-o-p def.), 1241 (C-O-C asym.), 1140, 1290 (S=O asym. and sym., respectively), 1740 (C=O) and 3400 cm^{-1} (OHstr).

p,p'-Bis(*N*-arylthioureidocarbonylmethoxyphenyl) sulphone (1): A mixture of *p,p'*-bis(carboxymethoxy)diphenylsulphone (3.66 g, 0.01 mol), thionyl chloride (2.5 ml) and chloroform (10 ml) was refluxed for 1 h. Excess thionyl chloride was then removed under reduced pressure and the residue was refluxed with phenyl thiourea (3.04 g, 0.02 mol) in chloroform (10 ml) for 3 h. The resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol-dioxane (3:1) solvent, (4.63 g, 73%), m.p. 146° (Found: C, 56.71; H, 4.09; N, 8.84. $C_{30}H_{26}N_4O_6S_2$ requires: C, 56.76; H, 4.12; N, 8.82%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1250 (C-O-C asym.), 1145, 1295 (S=O asym. and sym., respectively), 1670 (C=O amide-I sec.), 1510 (NH def. +CN str., amide-II sec.), 1295 (NH def. +CN str., amide-III sec.); δ (DMSO- d_6) 4.80 (4H, s, $2 \times ArOCH_2$), 7.02-8.00 (18H, m, $4 \times ArH$) and 10.04 (4H, s, $2 \times NHCSNHCO$).

Similarly, other phenyl thioureas were condensed with acid chloride (Table 1).

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Synthesis of some 2(*H*),4(*H*)-1,2,4-Triazino[3,4-*c*]-1,4-benzoxazin-5-ones

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It has been reported that some fused trizoles of 1,4-benzoxazin-3(2*H*)-ones exhibit diuretic¹ and other pharmacological properties^{2,3}. In view of these findings, the present paper describes the synthesis and characterisation of 2(*H*),4(*H*)-1,2,4-triazino[3,4-*c*]-1,4-benzoxazin-5-ones from the corresponding 1,4-benzoxazin-3(2*H*)-ones (Scheme 1), and study their antibacterial activity.

Scheme 1

As a representative case *o*-halophenol on condensation with chloroacetamide in ethanol in

Chart 1